

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF AVAILABILITY AND UTILIZATION OF ICT RESOURCES IN GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS IN CHAMBA DISTRICT OF HIMACHAL PRADESH

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Abstract

This study investigates the current state of digital infrastructure and the usage of ICT tools in government schools of the Chamba district, Himachal Pradesh. Through a survey of 99 school heads (GHS 30, GMS 18 and GSSS 51), we evaluated the availability of devices, internet access, training, and support mechanisms. While some progress is evident in infrastructure and teacher readiness, significant gaps persist in equitable access and effective implementation. The paper provides data-backed insights into challenges and suggests policy-level interventions to enhance digital learning outcomes.

1. Introduction:

ICT for education, which involves developing technology specifically for teaching and learning, and ICT in education, which refers to incorporating general ICT tools into the educational process (Okoro&Ekpo,2016). The advent of ICT has significantly impacted modern life, especially in the context of globalization.

Computer studies are important for all students because they teach a wide range of skills like logical thinking, creative design, problem-solving, and evaluation. Information and communication technology (ICT) has become very important for innovation and efficiency in many sectors worldwide. In education, ICT is a crucial part of the learning process both inside and outside the classroom. Using ICT creates a powerful learning environment and transform show students learn and teachers teach. ICT is not just a tool ; it's an important instrument to support new ways of teaching and learning. It should be used to develop students' skills .

Digital education has emerged as a cornerstone of modern pedagogy, with its integration gaining urgency post-COVID-19. Government schools, particularly in remote regions like Chamba, face unique barriers to adopting ICT tools effectively. Effective utilization goes beyond mere availability, encompassing how these tools are used to support curriculum delivery, student engagement, and administrative tasks. This research aims to assess the availability and utilization of digital tools across schools in the district, exploring how infrastructure, training, and policy support shape educational outcomes.

2. Methodology: The study used a structured questionnaire distributed to school heads (principals or in-charge) across Chamba's government schools. Data was collected on infrastructure (computers, internet, smart classrooms), access patterns, teacher preparedness, and perceived effectiveness. A total of 99 valid responses were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

2.1 Participation:

Heads of GSSS schools (51) form the largest group, comprising over half (52%) of the total responses. This ensures that the data strongly reflects the perspective of senior secondary schools, which are often more resource-rich and policy-aligned.

Whereas heads of 30 high schools (GHS) and 18 middle schools (GMS) also participating, the data captures a diverse educational landscape — from middle to senior secondary level.

Findings and Analysis:

3.1 Availability of Digital Infrastructure:

Internet and Wi-Fi Facility

A majority of schools (60 out of 99) schools (~61%) have access to the internet, indicating a strong foundation for digital learning and communication and 30 schools (~30%) also have Wi-Fi facility, enabling flexible and modern learning environments.

Number of e-classroom

73 out of 99 schools (~74%) have at least one e-classroom, showing strong integration of technology in teaching-learning. 19 schools (3+ e-classrooms) have multiple digital classrooms, enabling ICT-based instruction across grades and subjects. 6 schools have more than 5 e-classrooms, reflecting robust digital infrastructure. Only 26 schools (26%) currently lack e-classrooms, clearly identifying areas for targeted improvement.

Number of e-classroom

82 out of 99 schools (~83%) have at least one computer, enabling some form of digital access, 33 schools (33%) have 8 or more computers, 14 schools are particularly well-equipped, each having 10 or more computers, supporting advanced ICT initiatives. Only 17 schools (17%) currently lack computers.

Integrated Computer Projector

64 out of 99 schools (~65%) have at least one Integrated Computer Projector, enabling ICT-based teaching practices. **22 schools have 2 or more projectors**, improving accessibility across multiple classrooms. Only **30 schools** currently report having no projectors.

3.2 Digital Content and Curriculum Integration:

Maintenance of timetables for digital learning

Class wise timetables for digital learning were formally maintained in 68% of schools.

67 out of 99 schools (~68%) are already maintaining a class-wise timetable for e-learning, showing structured implementation of digital teaching practices. This

indicates that most schools are not only equipped with digital tools but are also organizing their use effectively. Only 30 schools have yet to adopt structured e-learning schedules, providing a clear scope for support and guidance

3.3 Teacher Readiness and Usage:

Teachers using ICT initiatives

71 out of 99 schools (~72%) have at least one teacher actively using ICT initiatives. **51 schools** have **5 or more teachers** using ICT in schools. Some schools report **20+ teachers** using ICT tools.

Teacher trained in using ICT

54 out of 99 schools (~55%) have at least one teacher trained in using ICT resources. A growing number of schools (21 schools) report having **5 or more trained teachers**. Several schools report **double-digit training participation**. 45 schools have no trained teachers yet.

Availability of IT Teachers

32 out of 99 schools (~32%) have at least one IT teacher, 11 schools have **2 or more IT teachers**, remaining 67 schools don't have any IT teacher.

Teacher providing online study material

80 out of 99 schools have at least one teacher providing online study material. Only 19 schools currently have no teacher involved in online material distribution. Schools with 3 to 7 teachers contributing make up a large portion (38 schools), showing strong team-based digital efforts.

3.4 Student Access and Usage:

Students' access to ICT

- **67 out of 99 schools** (approx. **67.7%**) reported that **students have access to ICT facilities** like computers or digital devices.

- **49 out of 99 schools (49.5%)** already provide **internet access to students**. This indicates that nearly **half of the schools** have taken meaningful steps to integrate the internet into classroom learning.

3.5 Perceptions and Effectiveness:

85 out of 99 schools (~86%) rated ICT as **Effective or Highly Effective** in enhancing student learning. **Nearly 40% of schools (39)** found ICT resources **highly effective**, indicating transformational impact in many classrooms. Only **6 schools (6%)** found ICT resources ineffective or not effective at all.

- However, usage remained superficial in many institutions due to resource gaps.

4. Challenges Identified:

- Insufficient devices and poor maintenance.
- Lack of technical support staff.
- Irregular electricity and internet in remote areas.
- Limited digital literacy among senior staff.

5. Discussion: While Chamba's schools reflect the broader national trends of digital expansion, the depth of usage remains shallow. The analysis clearly indicates that **availability does not guarantee utilization**. Even in schools equipped with digital tools, the

lack of trained personnel, maintenance support, and regular usage schedules hampers effective integration. Structural challenges, including inadequate budgets, limited technical support, and socio-economic disparities, hinder full-scale ICT integration. Yet, there is a growing acceptance and willingness among educators to use digital tools.

6. Recommendations:

- **Infrastructure Grants:** Dedicated funds for digital tools and internet setup, especially in remote blocks.
- **Strengthening Resource Centers:** Strengthening block-level digital resource centers.
- **Internet access:** Ensure reliable electricity and internet access in all schools.
- **Teacher Training:** Regular capacity-building programs for effective use of digital tools.
- **Monitoring & Evaluation:** Implement systems to track usage of digital classrooms and e-learning plans.
- **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs):** Engage with CSR and NGOs to sponsor digital infrastructure and training.

7. Conclusion: Digital education in Chamba's government schools shows potential but requires robust infrastructural and pedagogical support. This study reveals a substantial digital infrastructure gap in government schools of Chamba district. While a few schools are relatively better equipped, overall readiness for digital education remains low. Bridging the digital divide demands coordinated efforts from government bodies, educators, and local communities. With strategic investments and training, ICT can transform teaching-learning experiences even in remote regions like Chamba.

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